
THE QUESTIONS OF THE RATIONAL EFFICIENT USE RESURSNOGO POTENTIAL IN CONTEXT OF THE IMPROVEMENT TO TERRITORIAL ORGANIZATION PRODUCTION (ON EXAMPLE SOUTH ARAL REGION).

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Резюме.

Мақолада Қуйи Амударёнинг маъмурии районларида табиий- иқтисодий потенциалдан оқилона фойдаланиш масалалари ва регионнинг ишлаб чиқариш тармоқларининг худудий жойлашишини такомиллаштириш орқали бозор иқтисодиёти шаройтида унинг саморадарлига эришиш йиулари кўриб чиқилган.

Таянч сўзлар.

Салоҳият, мажмуали фойдаланиш, табиий манба, иқтисодий салоҳият, такомиллаштириш, Ороль минтаҳаси, саморадарлик, агро индустрал мажмуа.

Резюме.

В статье рассматриваются вопросы комплексного использования природно-экономического потенциала в контексте совершенствования территориальной организации отраслей производства в административных районах низовьев Амударьи в целях повышения эффективности экономики в условиях рыночных отношении.

Ключевые слова.

Потенциал, комплексные использование, природные источники, природный ресурс, совершенствование, эффективность, Аральский регион, агроиндустриальный комплекс.

Summary.

In article is considered questions of the complex use natural-economic potential in context improvement to territorial organization of the branches production in administrative region lower reached Amudarii in order to increase in market conditions.

Keywords

potential, intensification, specialization, acceleration, efficiency irrigation systems, resource, innovation, Agro-industrial complex.

In programme document of the Republic Uzbekistan on development of the production complex provided in nearest prospect main attention are spared rational use resource potential of the country as one of the main of the problems of the speed development of the economy of the country as a whole, in particular Republics Karakalpakstan, where concentrated enormous spares fuel-energy, mineral-raw materials and more than 2 mln. ga. 23% irrigated land of the fund and more than 48% pasture facility of the Republic Uzbekistan. However, degree actual освоённости irrigated lands forms lishi-2,5%. The Taken into accounted spares of iron ore 17 mlrd.tonn form in region Tebinbulaka, cookery salt Barsakelimeskogo birthplace-14 mlrd.tonn, but spares borax coal 7,0 mlrd.tonn form in areas of water Aral epidemic deaths and etc. The Multiple openings new, including row unique birthplace natural gas, oils on Ustyurte, wizened the day Aral epidemic deaths completely provide the organizations an oil-gaschemical, metallurgical and others branches industrial production. However, mastering natural resource and development is given birth-economic complex Lower reached Amudarii is closely connected with decision many scientifically-applied on its nature economic, social, technical and the other problems both republican and regional scale. To their it is necessary to refer the problems of the study Ustyurta and be of the bottom Arala, as well as irrigated land resource.

The Experience shows that without necessary source economic and geographical data, characterizing natural and social-economic ambience in territorial cut, impossible or is extremely labored development such project, as redistribution of the sewer Amudarii on branch facilities, making the large energy bases in zone of the production mastering Ustyurta. As well as, new centre to industry in zone influence to railway pathway Turtkuli-Nukus-Kungrad-Beyneu and others, which scientific provision requires the future direction of the economic mastering Northwest Uzbekistan as a whole. However, with tap in large scale Amudariinskih water on irrigation upper and at the average his(its) current, intensive development production in Lower reached Amudarii become very difficult. The Much of the irrigated lands already presently subject to secondary for salting and grows worse the land reclamation condition of the lands. As a result, in Lower reached Amudarii to appeared the complex complex ecological and social problems, having on level consequence the most harmful nature. Began the fall to productivities of the agricultural cultures, sharply changed the natural ambience and was thence saved up mass to negative ecological situation in all Priaralie Modern level social-economic development and involvement natural-economic

potential in economic turn in administrative region lower reached Amudarii is considered not sufficient. So for instance, region, disposing rich natural-raw materials resource, lags behind on production of the industrial product per capita in 1,4-1,5 with spare times less, than at the average on country. Moreover, industry of the region still has a nature of the primary conversion agricultural cheese and even in condition defect water resource.

The Territory lower reached Amudarii presents itself united production-territorial complex. This is connected with unity nationality problems them such as, united water problem, transport-telecommunication relationship, similarity agronomist specialization time for hydrodynamics to cycle production allows to consider him(it), as united economy-geographical region, which condition favour the organizations to general production specialization and creation all-round developed complex facilities type of the interstate free economic area. Considering these particularities of the region, it is necessary to spare emphases on making the base branches to industrial industry, as the most most important strategy of the speed development nationality complex whole Nizhneamudariinskogo region.

Mastering natural resource and development are given birth-economic complex of the region is closely connected with decision many scientifically-applied on its nature economic, social and the other problems as the general republican, so and regional scale. To their it is necessary to refer the problems, making the large energy bases in zone of the mastering Ustyurta, new centre to industry and others, which scientific provision requires the future direction of the economic mastering Priaraliya.

The Other problem, is directly connected with migration of the population. The Known that before recent time for Lower reached Amudarii were a typical more complex processes of the moving the population. On the one hand, constant and all increasing need for artificer to power caused the influx a specialist, with other - an administrative regions lower reached Amudarii, in particular Karakalpakstan from year because of Aral crisis per annum, loses the big contingent of the population, besides most activity and able-bodied his(its) part. The Effect this is a defect of the skilled personnel(frames) in different branch public facilities, in particular oil-chemical and gas industry. Intensive migration generates much difficulties in production and requires further, besides the most attentive dissidence studies of the development constructive and efficient ways of her(its) reduction. In connection with searching for of the ways of the fastening the personnel(frames) and making the happy circumstanceses for recovery social-

economic life north region lower reached Amudarii appropriately to concern the question about place, scale and direction of the development of the new branches of the production complex.

On the general volume of the product industry in administrative region lower reached Amudarii at the beginning initially 2013 has formed 1 трлн. 453,6 mlrd. bag that on 21,1 % more than in contrast with 2010. However she on rate of growth occupies amongst areas of the Republic Uzbekistan one of the last places, and does not answer her(its) raw materials and labor possibility. As a result in region irrational plant, plenty of types industrial product; this cotton wool and silk fabrics, chemical product, machines and equipment, refractory, ceramics, cement and other building materials; the paints, hardware. Regrettably, this problem possible was solve already presently on the base local raw materials resource In light said above, introduces expedient for instance, large centre oil-gas-chemical, ermine industrial with colour metallurgy, industrial bases agronomist cycle production, light industry and prolific.

Enormous value presents the decision of the problem of increasing drainage region. From suitable to irrigation arable lands is presently irrigated only 522-524 thous. ga. So prospecting of additional water, in particular transfer of excessive water from zone Karakumskogo channel and Arnasayskogo hydrophobia urgent need becomes in pool Aral epidemic deaths. Together with this needs serious and urgent work to reconstructions existing surd systems. Important increasing KPD irrigation systems introduces In this sense, selecting the agricultural cultures to condition lower reached Amudarii with reference to.

The Priority problem for mastering the novaja zeml'as in lower reached Amudarii, must become the first queue, irrigations north region, residing in zone of the influence Tahiatashskogo hydrodynamics, where will be formed not only cotton-luceme, but also multitapped territorial-production (agronomist) complexes.

In economic attitude, much it is important development stock-breeding. Her(its) role in salvaging bio deserted pasture and small labour content to branches wholly answer the permanent economic interest so it must save the important place in structure APK administrative region Lower reached Amudarii.

Today development lousy and вглубь production power in lower reached Amudarii goes by creation and improvement of the different territorial production structures, up to agronomist complex. In this connection one of the problems is a development of the types agricultural enterprise and ways of the mastering

natural-economic region for agricultural integer upon their the most essential directions.

For determination of the cost-performance of the agrarian sector of the Aral region, in particular Karakalpakistan, first of all we will value it on supplies efficient temperature, so required for development and bear fruit heat of the plants.

The Feature of the climate with standpoint of the agriculture shows that under other equal agronomist condition exists the certain interdependence between length vegetarian period, amount of the efficient temperature and productivity of the agricultural cultures. So, between facilities located on extreme south and north point cotton grower, there are differences in length vegetarian period with the temperature above +100C (in Turtkul 205 days, in Kungrad 186 days), in amount of the efficient temperature (above +100C) in Turtkul -22580C, in Kungrad -19140C. Thereby, study result grow cotton plant in experimental facilities shows that, as from south region, reduction to length vegetation period with the temperature above +100C on 1 day brings about reduction of the potential productivity of the cotton plant on 1 centner approximately. So displacement much (except facilities) of the sowing areas of the cotton plant with North on South that was reasonable and with standpoint state interest As a result, in condition South region by increasing to productivities 27,9 c with hectare, annual production of the cotton-product in its raw state can reach 192,5 thousands tons, in central and in north region, with provision for reductions of the sowing of the cotton plant on 35%-40% possible get 116,1 thousands tons of the pat at productivities 22,6 c with hectare. In condition of north region this will bring about expansion of the sowing areas other corn cultures.

Today, development in extent in and deeper production power to rural terrain, in region goes the way of the creation and improvement of the different territorial production structures from shop on conversion cheese, up to agro industrial complex and salve, triangle "Kungrad-Usyurt (SURGILI)=SEVERNAYAH=URGA". A development of the types production enterprise and ways of the mastering resource potential of the region is In this connection one of the problems upon their the most essential directions. One of their main of the directions scientifically exploratory searching for will is connected with problem of the organizations, optimized territorial structure facilities, economic region in Lower reached Amudarii. In this connection, in agrarian sector with provision for improvements agrotechnology agricultural cultures, introduction to enabling technologies water of the use, undertaking the capital

planning by flap, will is motivated irrigation rate have eaten that will allow to increase the irrigated area and enlarge the volume to product of the husbandry. In this connection, the most further improvement to specialization and territorial accomodation of the branches of the agriculture in south region will go on way of the increase production pat product in its raw state, silk cocoon, fruit and grape, as well as expansions of the area of the breeding sheep. In central and north region alongside with intensification of the husbandry sowings cotton plant do not enlarge, but branches to industry will develop, basically, on conversion of the product APK. It Is Expected intensive development grain vegetable mellon of the cultures and stock-breeding, for what there are corresponding to condition. In Aral region, disposing enormous caught pasture and fertile lands, is provided the most further development vegetable-mellons, grain, animal; meat of the milk direction. Thereby, involvement in economic turn reserve production and new type useful fossilized, eventually, will promote shaping the branches to industry producing mineral fertilizer, chemical of protection plant on the base resource potential of the region. Thereby, involvement in agric turn unused reserve production by deepening the intensive methods of the introduction production, as well as with provision for optimization of the branch structure of the agrarian sector, possible in addition get annually-0,394 million ton grain, 0,297-0,301 million tons of the cotton-product in its raw state. Thereby, involvement in agric turn unused reserve production by deepening the intensive methods of the introduction production, as well as with provision for optimization of the branch structure of the agrarian sector, possible in addition get annually-0,404 million ton grain, 0,291-0,300 million tons of the cotton-product in its raw state.

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